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GRAPHENE-BASED MATERIALS AS STRAIN SENSORS IN FIBRE/EPOXY MODEL COMPOSITES

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Background

Phys Rev B, 79 (20) (2009), p. 205433

Strain sensing of graphene by using Raman spectroscopy

- ❖ Due to the existence of the large strain-induced Raman band shift, Raman spectroscopy can follow the deformation behaviour of graphene.
- ❖ Graphene's 2D nature and its resonantly enhanced Raman peaks make it a perfect candidate for strain sensors.
- ❖ The similar technique can also be employed for some high-performance fibres, such as para-aramid fibres and carbon fibres, and other 2D materials like MoS₂.

Background

- ✓ Fibre reinforced composites are gaining increasing attentions.
- ✓ Compared with conventional test methods, the technique of using graphene as strain sensors with the help of Raman in a fibre reinforced composite can be:
 - real-time, *in-situ*, point-by-point, non-destructive, etc.
- ✓ Due to graphene' 2D nature, it is easy to coat and can act as large-area strain sensors which can be adapted for a wide range of applications.

Polymer 2010, 51 (9), 2033-2039, Comp. Sci. and Tech. 2009, 69 (10), 1547-1552.

Glass fibres coated with graphene nanoplatelets

Elicarb[®] material grade graphene
(Thomas Swan & Co. Ltd.)

A type of commercially-available multi-layer graphene nanoplatelets with an average lateral size of $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$

Electrochemically-exfoliated graphene (EG)

Glass fibres coated with graphene nanoplatelets

Characterisation of Elicarb[®] and EG graphene nanoplatelets

Glass fibres coated with graphene nanoplatelets

SEM images of (a) as-received, (b) Elicarb[®] graphene and (c) EG graphene nanoplatelets coated glass fibers

- ❖ The lateral size of graphene nanoplatelets varies;
- ❖ Elicarb[®] graphene flakes appear to be thicker than EG graphene.

Glass fibres coated with graphene nanoplatelets

Strain sensitivity of (a) Elicarb[®] and (b) EG graphene nanoplatelets coated on glass fibres before being embedded in the epoxy matrix

The strain sensitivity of graphene nanoplatelets can be affected by factors such as **aspect ratio** and **functionalities**.

Glass fibres coated with graphene nanoplatelets

Strain reporting at the fibre-matrix interface using EG nanoplatelets

The strain reported by EG graphene scattered but was still in good agreement with the shear-lag analysis.

$$\varepsilon_f = \varepsilon_m \left[1 - \frac{\cosh\beta(l/2 - x)}{\cosh\beta l/2} \right]$$

$$\beta = \left[\frac{2G_m}{E_f r^2 \ln\left(\frac{R}{r}\right)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\tau = E_f \frac{r}{2} \left[\frac{d\varepsilon_f}{dx} \right]$$

Glass fibres coated with CVD graphene

Glass fibres coated with CVD graphene

The CVD graphene remained mostly **defect-free** and **monolayer** after being transferred onto fibres.

Glass fibres coated with CVD graphene

Strain reporting performance of CVD graphene in glass fibre/epoxy model composites investigated by Raman spectroscopy

Glass fibres coated with CVD graphene

Cyclic deformation of CVD graphene coating

The strain reporting performance of CVD graphene is **sensitive** and **reversible** at low strain levels.

Glass fibres coated with CVD graphene

Strain reported by CVD graphene in a glass fibre/epoxy model composite

Point-by-point strain reporting can be achieved by CVD graphene coating. The reported data is **high-resolution** and **stable**.

Glass fibres coated with CVD graphene

Strain reported by CVD graphene in a glass fibre/epoxy model composite

The strain reporting performance of CVD graphene was **partially reversible** even after exceeding the upper limit of its strain range.

Comparison of fibres coated with:

Graphene nanoplatelets

Discontinuous, limited aspect ratio,
inconsistent in dimensional and
chemical properties

CVD graphene

Continuous, high aspect ratio and
homogeneous

Conclusions

- This project has demonstrated the use of both discontinuous graphene nanoplatelets and CVD graphene as strain sensors in glass fibre/epoxy model composites using Raman spectroscopy and their sensing abilities were compared.
- It has been shown that the strain sensitivity of graphene nanoplatelets can be affected by factors such as the aspect ratio and chemical compositions.
- The inconsistency in both dimensional and chemical properties among individual graphene flakes causes scatter in the reported data.
- Compared with graphene nanoplatelets, the strain sensing ability of CVD graphene was more sensitive, accurate and stable due to its high aspect ratio and homogeneity in both dimension and chemical properties. Its strain reporting performance remained reversible and reliable at low strain levels (<0.6% strain) above which the breakdown of the interface can be observed.

Thank you for attention!

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